

Multidisciplinary Team Approaches in the Management of Diabetic Foot Complications: Integration of Emergency Medicine, General Surgery, and Orthopedics"

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Abstract: Objective: This study was designed to retrospectively analyze the clinical data of patients with diabetic foot in the MIHS Provincial Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal and to explore the therapeutic effect of Multidisciplinary Team (MDT) on diabetic foot.

Methods: Data were collected from 169 patients with diabetic foot admitted to the Department of Surgery (Orthopedics), MIHS Provincial Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal from January 2018 to December 2022. According to whether they received MDT treatment during hospitalization, they were divided into 81 cases of MDT group and 88 cases of non-MDT group. All patients completed routine examination after admission. The number of operations, the rate of toe (limb), the time of wound healing, the number of hospital stays, the hospitalization cost, the positive rate of wound bacteria, the wound healing in different time periods, and the second postoperative operation were analyzed. Statistical analysis was performed on the second results of white blood cells, red blood cells, hemoglobin, albumin, C-reactive protein, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, total cholesterol, triglyceride and low-density lipoprotein. Many professional figures, Emergency Medicine, Surgeons (both General and Orthopedics), Radiologists, Specialized Nurses are called to apply their knowledges to the diabetic patients affected by diabetic foot in a virtuous circle leading to reach the goals, with the imperative action of the Multidisciplinary Team. Organized center will allow both a correct and rapid diagnosis, the use in ambulatorial environments of modern tools, or the hospitalization in multitasking wards, in which all the complications and the necessary treatments are possible, both in emergencies or in elective way, both considering revascularizations and surgery.

Results: Of the 169 patients, 75 were cured, 73 were improved, 18 were unhealed, and 3 died. The number of wound operation in MDT group was 2.37 ± 1.67 times, in non-MDT group was 3.36 ± 2.07 times ($t=1.186$, $P<0.05$); the rate of toe (limb) amputation in MDT group was 17.28% and 37.50% in non-MDT group ($P<0.05$); hospitalization days in the MDT group were 34.23 ± 6.36 days, in the non-MDT group were 43.54 ± 7.33 days ($t=2.537$, $P<0.05$); hospitalization expenses in the MDT group were 4.28 ± 3.88 million, and non-MDT group hospitalization expenses 6.11 ± 3.81 million ($t=2.851$, $P<0.05$); 43 cases of 169 diabetic foot disease were positive for pathogen culture, mainly Gram-negative bacteria, accounting for 65.11% (28/43) and Gram Positive bacteria accounted for 34.8% (15/43). The recurrence rate was 4.63% in the MDT group and 12.53% in the non-MDT group ($P<0.05$). The statistical analysis showed that the P values in both groups were less than 0.05, which was statistically significant.

Conclusion: Diabetic foot treatment by MDT can effectively control wound infection, reduce the number of dressing changes, reduce the amputation rate, shorten hospitalization time and the cost, improve patient prognosis and improve patients' quality of life. It is a new and efficient diagnosis and treatment model which is worth promoting.

Keywords: diabetic foot; Multidisciplinary treatment (MDT); infection; limb amputation; wound repair

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Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) describes diabetes as the most common metabolic disorder worldwide, with approximately 9% of adult men and 8% of adult women suffering from the disease, and 15% to 20% of people with diabetic foot is rapidly becoming a disease with a serious global burden [1]. Diabetic foot (DF) was first proposed by Oakley. In 1999, WHO defined diabetic foot as infection, ulcer and/or deep tissue of the foot associated with neurological abnormalities in the distal lower extremity and various degrees of peripheral vascular disease at or below the ankle joint in 1999. destroy [2]. According to the Chinese guidelines for the prevention and treatment of type 2 diabetes (2017 edition) [3], the prevalence of type 2 diabetes in domestic adults has risen from 0.67% to 10.4% (2013) in the past 40 years, of which diabetic foot patients accounted for 1.2%-2.7%. Multiple factors are involved in the pathogenesis of DF. The course of disease is long, the condition is complex, the patient's psychological and economic burden is heavy, and the quality of life and prognosis are seriously damaged. It is one of the serious chronic complications that lead to disability and death in diabetic patients[4]. If the subtle damage to the feet of diabetic patients is not treated in time, ulcers, gangrene and even amputation of toes (limbs) are prone to occur. About 40% to 60% of non-traumatic amputations occur in patients with diabetic feet [5]. Traditional single-specialty treatment of DF cannot achieve good results, which may be due to the involvement of multiple disciplines such as wound repair, endocrinology, nephrology, cardiology, infection, orthopedics, and vascular surgery. The ideal working model is to establish a diabetic foot treatment center in a hospital, and under the coordination of wound repair surgery, multidisciplinary division of labor and cooperation will jointly complete the clinical treatment of DF. Therefore, in 2015, the International Diabetic Foot Working Group (IWGDF) issued the "International Clinical Consensus on Diabetic Foot" [6], emphasizing that according to the individual needs of patients, multidisciplinary cooperation should be used to reduce the incidence of diabetic foot, the number of amputations and related medical treatment. cost. The multidisciplinary collaborative diagnosis and treatment model [7] (Multidisciplinary Team, MDT) is an emerging treatment model based on the "patient-centered" medical model in the world. It mainly covers the diagnosis, treatment and management of peripheral arterial disease, foot infection, interventions to promote ulcer healing, and decompression therapy (including the choice of footwear), blood glucose management and nutritional management are the basic links [8]. At present, our centre has preliminarily established DF multidisciplinary diagnosis and treatment normative indicators and procedures, providing a framework for the comprehensive management of DF patients, but it still needs to be further improved and verified in practice [9]. In the MDT model, all clinical specialties can get close cooperation, everything is patient-centered, starting from the interests of patients, looking at the problem from a holistic perspective [10], and integrating the treatment plans of each specialty through mutual communication between various specialists, learn from each other, provide a more comprehensive assessment and the most suitable and authoritative treatment plan for the patient, but consider the regional differences and individual differences of patients for the different sex, we need individualized treatment for patients with different conditions. This study retrospectively analyzed the clinical data of diabetic foot patients in the general surgery ward of department of Surgery, MIHS Provincial Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal observed and analyzed the treatment effect of the diabetic foot MDT model, and the shortcomings of our hospital's implementation of this model place.

Research Methodology

This study retrospectively analyzed the data of 169 diabetic foot patients who met the screening criteria and were treated in the department of Surgery (Orthopaedics), MIHS Provincial Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal from January 2018 to December 2022 group (81 cases) and non-MDT group (88 cases).

Clinical data of diabetic foot patients

General information: name, gender, age, duration of diabetes, duration of diabetic foot disease, wound location, Wagner classification, complications, comorbidities, follow-up history, etc.

Screening criteria for diabetic foot patients

Inclusion criteria: (1) Type 2 Diabetes Prevention and Treatment Guidelines Diabetes Diagnostic Criteria [11], and be identified as diabetic foot patients according to the diabetic foot examination method and diagnostic criteria; (2) Diabetic foot Wagner grade 0-5; (3) did not give up treatment or be discharged without completion of treatment.

Exclusion criteria: (1) Incomplete information; (2) Unconscious and uncooperative patients; (3) Severe underlying disease and poor general condition; (4) Patients with malignant tumors; (5) Exclude diabetic patients who are pregnant; (6) Patients using drugs that affect wound healing: such as glucocorticoids, etc.

Treatment

MDT group: After admission, according to the first diagnosis and treatment standard of MDT, The complete patient's course of disease, past history, complication history, DF medical history and treatment history, personal history, blood vessel examination, nerve examination, wound examination, laboratory examination, bacterial smear, wound surface Secretion culture, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, CRP, procalcitonin, foot X-ray, ABI, lower extremity vascular color Doppler ultrasound, Wagner classification, etc., to evaluate the patient's general condition and formulate a diagnosis and treatment plan. After admission, the wound was rinsed repeatedly with hydrogen peroxide and normal saline, paying special attention to the deep wound with sinus passage. After washing, tissue scissors or surgical blades were used to remove part of the necrotic tissue in the wound, and ointment mupirocin or dry dressing was used to cover the wound. Standardized blood sugar management: Insulin preparations are the first choice for hypoglycemic drugs, and individual plans are formulated according to the CDS guidelines for diabetes prevention and treatment (glycosylated hemoglobin HbA1c<7%), blood sugar is monitored and blood sugar is adjusted in strict accordance with the opinions of endocrinology experts. Generally, preoperative blood sugar is controlled at 7.8 ~10.0mmol/L. Nutritional management norms: Evaluate the nutritional status of the patient based on the results of the physical examination and examination, assess whether blood transfusion, albumin supplementation, etc. are needed to improve the general condition of the patient. Adjust the patient's dietary intake according to the advice of the nutrition department. Standards for diagnosis and treatment of vascular and neuropathy: Peripheral nerve degeneration and vascular lesions are the pathophysiological basis of diabetic foot. Patients admitted to the hospital routinely undergo color Doppler ultrasound, CTA or DSA examination of lower extremity vessels to understand vascular lesions and ischemia of lower extremities[12]. At the same time, drugs such as pentoxifylline and vitamin B were used to improve microcirculation and nourish the nerves. The blood pressure of patients with hypertension should be strictly controlled below 140/90mmHg. It is recommended to use ACEI or ARB antihypertensive drugs, and the adjustment should be assisted by a cardiovascular physician. For patients with abnormal lipid metabolism, statins or combined with fibrates should be given to regulate lipid levels, and control LDL-C <2.6mmol/L, TG <5.7mmol/L. For patients with different degrees of renal disease, nephrologists will assist in the adjustment and monitoring of renal function. Fundus examination was used to assess the degree of retinopathy in patients. Infection diagnosis and treatment standard: Most of the wounds of patients on admission are infected wounds, and broad-spectrum antibiotics are given empirically for anti-infection,

adjusted according to the results of wound secretion culture and drug sensitivity test, and sensitive narrow-spectrum antibiotics are used instead, broad-spectrum drug-resistant bacteria and common. When the infection cannot be controlled by antibiotics, use high-level antibiotics or combined drugs according to the opinions of the Department of general surgery and the Department of orthopaedics (such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, carbapenem-resistant bacteria, etc.). Routine X-ray examination is performed to determine whether there is bone tissue destruction, periosteal reaction, foreign bodies, etc. If necessary, perform MRI to evaluate the presence of soft tissue infection and osteomyelitis. If osteomyelitis is confirmed, the duration of antibiotic treatment should be at least 6 weeks. When the osteomyelitis reaches a moderate degree of infection, the effect of antibiotic treatment is not good, and urgent and early debridement is required. Surgery, early surgery can remove necrotic soft tissue, reduce the pressure on the infected site, and eliminate local microcirculation abnormalities caused by infection. In addition, since the level of amputation is related to the age of tissue infection, early debridement can avoid major amputation.

Standards for diagnosis and treatment of decompression: Diabetic foot patients are often accompanied by neuropathy and are not sensitive to pressure. Skin ulceration is more common due to uneven stress on ordinary shoes. Choose loose, stable, and breathable cotton old shoes and socks to reduce pain. Extremity plantar pressure is helpful to prevent or prevent foot ulceration and infection again. For patients with severe sensory impairment and nerve entrapment, Dellon triple nerve decompression surgery can be considered.

Standards for wound diagnosis and treatment: (1) Non-surgical treatment: When changing wound dressings, use tissue scissors to remove clear necrotic tissue and reduce the chance of infection under the premise of avoiding active bleeding and excessive damage to healthy tissue. Choose different drugs and wound dressings according to the different stages of the wound, increase the frequency of dressing changes during the severe infection period, remove necrotic tissue and secretions in time, and use antibacterial and scab-dissolving mainly; when basal granulation tissue begins to proliferate, use antibacterial drugs (Such as mupirocin ointment, compound polymyxin B ointment) and growth-promoting drugs (such as fibroblast growth factor, epidermal growth factor, etc.) mixed use. (2) Surgical treatment: If the patient's foot condition is not life-threatening, chronic ulcer repair + negative pressure wound therapy (NPWT) will be performed after the patient's blood sugar control is stable and the blood supply of blood vessels in the lower extremities is improved. If the patient has severe foot infection and untimely surgery may lead to a rise in the amputation (limb) level or even life-threatening conditions, debridement surgery should be performed as soon as possible. In principle, the wound is not sutured at one stage during the operation, and the infected and necrotic soft tissue and tendons are removed during the operation. If there is bone exposure, part of the bone cortex is bitten off with a rongeur, and the surrounding soft tissue is surrounded by bone and sutured layer by layer or local skin flap transfer. Toe (limb) amputation should be performed for those with obvious bone necrosis. The plane of amputation should be higher than the level of gangrene to avoid unhealed wound or re-amputation of toe (limb) due to poor blood supply. The wound should be covered with NPWT foam dressing. NPWT strongly stimulates granulation growth through intermittent negative pressure suction (suction for 5 minutes, pause for 3 minutes), improves capillary circulation, stimulates capillary proliferation, significantly improves wound blood flow, reduces infection, effectively reduces the area and volume of dead space, and eliminates dead space, to provide favorable conditions for later wound repair [13]. Negative Pressure Wound Therapy Instillation (NPWTi) [14] is often used for wounds with excessive exudation and severe infection. After the condition of the wound surface improves, the wound surface can be closed by direct suture, skin graft or flap transplantation in the later stage.

Popularization of health education: Strengthen relevant knowledge education for patients and their families, and provide patients and their families with health education plans for diabetic feet. Quit smoking, strengthen foot care, trim nails correctly, treat corns and minor wounds in time, check your feet daily, etc.

Non-MDT group: Complete relevant blood tests after admission, with wound treatment as the primary goal. When blood sugar fluctuates greatly and is poorly controlled, please consult an endocrinologist to assist in adjusting blood sugar. Patients with lower extremity pain, claudication, weakened dorsalis pedis artery pulse, and low skin temperature

should undergo color Doppler ultrasound, CTA and other vascular examinations. If the indicators are abnormal, please consult a General surgeon. Physician consultation and assessment of vascular conditions and further treatment. If there are abnormal indicators such as blood pressure and blood lipids, please consult with the relevant departments such as the Department of medicine, General Practice and Emergency Medicine. Albumin, erythrocytes, hemoglobin, electrolytes, etc. should be replenished in time when they are below the standard. The general condition, infection and wound treatment of the patients were the same as those of the MDT group.

Observation indicators

White blood cell count, hemoglobin level, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, C-reactive protein, admission random blood glucose, glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), plasma albumin, total cholesterol (TC), triglyceride (TG), low-density lipoprotein (LDL-C), high-density lipoprotein (HDL-C), ankle-brachial index (ABI), number of operations, toe amputation (limb) rate, positive rate of wound bacteria, wound healing, length of hospitalization, hospitalization expenses, etc. Follow-up for recurrence within 3 months Rate.

Data analysis

This experiment adopts retrospective analysis, and uses GraphPad Prism6 to analyze and summarize the collected data. Measurement data are expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation, and t test is used for comparison between two samples; count data (n, %) are expressed, and χ^2 test is used for comparison, $P < 0.05$ means the difference is statistically significant.

Results and discussion

General characteristics of patients with diabetic foot

From January 2018 to December 2022, among the 186 diabetic foot patients admitted in the Department of Surgery (Orthopaedics), MIHS Provincial Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal, 169 cases met the inclusion criteria, including 115 males (68.2%) and 54 females (31.8%). The ratio of male to female was 2.1:1; the average age of analysis was 59.5 years old (27-94 years old, 59.5 ± 11.6), among which the majority of patients were 50-69 years old, accounting for 56% (see Table 1). The average duration of diabetes was 9.31 years (0-22 years, 9.31 ± 7.35), and the average duration of diabetic foot disease was 2.13 months (0-9 months, 2.13 ± 2.03). There were 191 wounds in 169 patients, including toes (82 cases), heels (13 cases), soles (38 cases), dorsum of feet (46 cases), and ankles (12 cases) (see Table 2). Of the 169 diabetic foot patients, 43 cases were positive for wound pathogenic bacteria, mainly Gram-negative bacteria (28, 65.11%), Gram-positive bacteria (15, 34.8%) (See Table 3). 63 cases (63/169) were admitted with hypertension; 32 cases (32/169) with coronary heart disease; 37 cases (37/169) with diabetic retinopathy; 51 cases (51/169) with diabetic nephropathy. Mainly (62.7%); 78 cases (78/169) of peripheral neuropathy; 48 cases (48/169) of dyslipidemia; 36 cases (36/169) of arteriosclerosis, of which 23 cases (14.4%) of There were 35 cases (35/169) of local osteonecrosis.

Table 1 Age distribution of diabetic foot patients

Age(years)	Number of cases (n=169)	Constituent ratio (%)
<30	1	0.59
30-39	7	4.14
40-49	25	14.79
50-59	49	28.99
60-69	46	27.22
70-79	37	21.89

>80	4	2.37
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Table 2 Distribution of wound locations in two groups of patients

Wound distribution	Number of cases (n=191)	Constituent ratio (%)
toes	82	43
instep	46	24
heel	13	7
sole	38	20
ankle	12	6

Table 3 Bacteria distribution in wounds of diabetic foot patients in two groups

pathogenic bacteria	Number of cases (n=43)	Constituent ratio (%)
G⁺	15	34.8
Staphylococcus aureus	5	11.6
Staphylococcus epidermidis	5	11.6
Staphylococcus haemolyticus	5	11.6
G⁻	28	65.11
Klebsiella pneumoniae	7	16.3
Escherichia coli	10	23.2
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	11	25.6

Table 4 Comparison of the general conditions of the two groups of patients

	MDT group (n=81)	Non-MDT group (n=88)
Age	58.80±11.50	59.90±7.07
Duration of diabetes (years)	8.70±3.54	8.36±2.54
Duration of diabetic foot disease (months)	3.32±2.27	2.54±2.69
ABI		
Left	0.89±0.35	0.91±0.30
right	0.78±0.29	0.85±0.38
WBC (10 ⁹ /L)	11.72±6.48	10.39±5.29
RBC (10 ¹² /L)	3.59±0.61	3.75±0.70
Hb (g/L)	104.37±20.56	107.30±20.66
CRP (mg/L)	81.02±72.09	78.70±65.36
ESR	83.05±37.35	82.39±42.19
Plasma albumin (g/L)	30.98±5.34	32.44±6.45
admission random blood glucose	14.10±6.98	14.14±7.64
HbA1c (%)	9.21±3.89	9.69±4.34
Total Cholesterol (TC)	4.56±1.58	4.85±1.69
Triglycerides (TG)	3.51±0.54	3.15±0.48
LDL-C (mmol/L)	2.56±1.22	2.64±1.91
HDL-C (mmol/L)	0.80±0.40	0.84±0.38

Note: After the data of the MDT group and the non-MDT group were tested by t test, P<0.05 indicated statistical significance, and P>0.05 indicated no statistical significance. There was no significant difference between the above two groups of data, and there was no statistical significance.

Two treatment outcomes of diabetic foot patients

There were statistically significant positive rates of WBC, plasma albumin, HbA1c, CRP, TC, LDL-C, and bacteria in the second postoperative blood test between the MDT group and the non-MDT group (see Tables 5 and 6). Of the 169 patients, 75 were cured, 73 were improved, 18 were not cured, and 3 died (see Table 7). The cure rate of the MDT group was 55.6% within 30-40 days, and that of the non-MDT group was 43.2%. $P < 0.05$ was statistically significant. Comparing the data between the two groups, 81 patients in the MDT group underwent an average of 2.37 operations, including 2 cases of amputation (ankle disarticulation), 12 cases of toe amputation, 35 cases of skin grafting, and 32 cases of direct suture. The 88 patients in the non-MDT group underwent an average of 3.36 operations, including amputation in 2 cases, toe amputation in 31 cases, skin grafting in 37 cases, skin flap in 2 cases, and direct suture in 17 cases. The hospitalization expenses, number of operations, number of dressing changes after operation, rate of amputation (limb) and recurrence rate of 3-month follow-up in the MDT group were lower than those in the non-MDT group ($P < 0.05$) (see Table 8).

Table 5 Comparison of the general information of the two groups after the second postoperative period ($\bar{x} \pm s$)

	MDT group (n=81)	Non-MDT group (n=88)	P value
WBC ($10^9/L$)	6.01±2.36	10.16±3.65*	<0.05
RBC ($10^{12}/L$)	3.18±1.46	3.34±1.67	>0.05
Hb (g/L)	103.00±6.75	101.00±7.07	>0.05
CRP (mg/L)	15.87±16.24	18.94±16.60*	<0.05
ESR	14.06±12.91	15.22±13.39	>0.05
Plasma albumin (g/L)	31.20±4.15	29.80±3.69*	<0.05
HbA1c (%)	8.32±2.89	9.20±3.54*	<0.05
Total Cholesterol (TC)	3.21±1.05	3.52±1.75*	<0.05
Triglycerides (TG)	3.18±0.67	3.24±0.51	>0.05
LDL-C (mmol/L)	2.02±0.89	2.28±0.75*	<0.05
HDL-C (mmol/L)	1.20±0.47	0.90±0.43	>0.05
ABI			
Left	0.93±0.08	0.90±0.07	>0.05
right	0.94±0.13	0.91±0.09	>0.05

Note: The data of WBC, plasma albumin, HbA1c, CRP, TC, and LDL-C in the MDT group and the non-MDT group were tested by t test, and it was found that $P < 0.05$ was statistically significant; the rest were not statistically significant.

Table 6 Comparison of wound culture results after the second postoperative wound between the two groups

	admission		2nd postoperative	
	MDT group	non-MDT group	MDT group	non-MDT group
positive cases	42	52	28	36
Negative cases	39	36	53	52
Positive rate (%)	51.9%	59.1%	34.6%	50.9%

Note: After the data of the MDT group and the non-MDT group were tested by χ^2 , the data of the two groups were $P < 0.05$, which was statistically significant.

Table 7 Relationship between Wagner grade and prognosis

Wagner classification	Number of cases (%)	heal(%)	Improved (%)	Unhealed (%)	die(%)
level 0	0 (0)	0	0	0	0
level 1	21 (12.4)	18	3	0	0
level 2	78 (46.2)	33	37	5	0
level 3	32 (18.9)	13	17	2	0
level 4	20 (11.8)	7	9	3	1
level 5	18 (10.7)	4	7	5	2
total	169	75 (44.4)	73 (43.2)	18 (10.6)	3 (1.8)

Table 8 Comparison of length of hospitalization, hospitalization expenses, number of operations, dressing changes, rate of toe (limb) amputation, and recurrence rate between the two groups of patients

	MDT group (n=81)	Non-MDT group (n=88)	P value
Days of hospitalization (d)	34.23±6.36	43.54±7.33*	<0.05
Hospital expenses (10,000 yuan)	4.28±3.88	6.11±3.81*	<0.05
Number of operations	2.37±1.67	3.36±2.07*	<0.05
The number of dressing changes after surgery	6.23±1.58	12.75±2.37*	<0.05
Amputation rate	17.28%	37.50%*	<0.05
3-month follow-up recurrence rate	4.63%	12.53%*	<0.05

Note: The number of days of hospitalization (d), hospitalization expenses (10,000 yuan), number of operations, number of dressing changes after surgery, rate of toe (limb) amputation, and recurrence rate at 3-month follow-up had statistically significant differences ($P<0.05$).

Typical cases

Case A: Patient shyam sah, male, 70 years old, was admitted to the hospital due to "ischemic necrosis of the left big toe for more than 3 months". Diabetes has been found for 15 years, and hemodialysis has continued for 10 years with uremia (3 times/week). Examination: The left foot was red and swollen, the skin part of the first metatarsal was blackened, the first toe was blackened and necrotic, the periwound was red and swollen, the smell was heavy, the pulse of the dorsalis pedis artery was weakened, the peripheral blood supply was poor, and the pain was dull. Admission diagnosis: type 2 diabetic foot disease (left), type 2 diabetes, hypertension, uremia. After admission, debridement and dressing were performed. Because the patient was a uremic patient, the use of anesthetics and antibiotics was relatively limited, and the inflammation control effect was not good. After evaluating the patient's tolerance, the "left foot chronic ulcer repair + NPWT + first Toe amputation", the rongeur bites off the necrotic bone, removes the necrotic tissue of the wound, cleans it, stops the bleeding thoroughly, trims the foam dressing to the size of the wound, and washes the wound with NPWTi. After 7 days, the negative pressure device was removed and the wound surface was smaller than before. The base was fresher than before. "Left foot chronic ulcer repair + NPWT" was performed several times. , Poor compliance, conservative treatment with wound debridement and dressing change, the wound gradually healed, during which the patient's condition was regularly and regularly assessed by MDT, blood pressure, blood lipids, hemodialysis, nutritional support and other general conditions were adjusted, the wound was healed and discharged, and the hospital stay was 106 days .

Case B: Patient Mohan das, a 48-year-old male, was admitted to our department in July because of skin ulceration on his right foot. He had a history of hypertension for 15 years. On admission, the random blood glucose was 12mmol/L, WBC 15.19*10⁹/L, Hb 86 g/L, and albumin 25.5g/L. MRA showed that the right plantar and dorsalis pedis arteries were not clearly displayed, suggesting atherosclerosis. Severe sensory disturbance in right foot sensory threshold. Fundus retinal hemorrhage and exudation can be seen. Admission diagnosis: type 2 diabetic foot disease (right), type 2 diabetes, hypertension. After being admitted to the hospital, the relevant examinations are completed, and MDT experts provide professional treatment opinions, adjust blood sugar according to laboratory indicators, control blood pressure, supplement albumin in an appropriate amount, regulate lipids to stabilize plaque, improve microcirculation, etc., perform wound cleaning and dressing, and anti-inflammation throughout the body. After the signs were stable, the "chronic ulcer repair + NPWT + amputation of the first toe" was performed under regional block anesthesia on the right lower extremity. The negative pressure was removed 7 days after the operation and some necrotic tissue remained. Under anesthesia, "chronic ulcer repair + NPWT" was performed again. After 7 days, the negative pressure was removed

and the growth of stump granulation tissue was acceptable, with a little necrotic tissue remaining. The third "chronic ulcer repair + skin grafting + NPWT" was performed 10 days later. After removal of the negative pressure, it was found that the skin graft grew well, and a little wound base on the distal dorsum of the foot was not good, with a little exudation. After 5 dressing changes, the wound was cured and discharged.

Case C: Patient Phulo devi sada, a 55-year-old female, was admitted to the hospital due to "right foot ulceration for more than 1 month". She had a history of diabetes for more than 17 years. Physical examination: the skin of the right foot was red and swollen, the skin temperature increased, and the tenderness was obvious. The right toe was black with foul odor. The right dorsalis pedis pulse was weakened. Admission diagnosis: type 2 diabetic foot disease (right), type 2 diabetes. Complete relevant examinations after admission, white blood cells $14.92 \times 10^9/L$, hemoglobin 89g/L, albumin 19.4g/L, MRA of lower extremity vessels showed: sclerotic changes and stenosis of the upper and middle femoral arteries on both sides, upper right peroneal artery and posterior tibial artery. The upper part of the artery was narrowed, and multiple collateral circulation vessels formed around the calf of the foot. According to MDT analysis, the patient should be treated as soon as possible to deal with blood vessels, hypoproteinemia, and control inflammation. The vascular surgeon performed percutaneous balloon angioplasty under local anesthesia to open the superficial femoral artery and peroneal artery. After the operation, the pulse of the dorsum of the foot was significantly enhanced, and the skin temperature increased. To improve the general condition of the patient, "right foot chronic ulcer repair + NPWT + 1st to 4th toe amputation" was performed under general anesthesia on the 10th day after admission, thoroughly debride the wound, bite out the necrotic bone, clean, thoroughly stop bleeding, remove the negative The pressure device found that the wound surface was fresher than before, and performed "right foot chronic ulcer repair + NPWT" again. During the treatment, the fifth toe of the right foot was necrotic and was amputated. In the third operation, skin grafting + NPWT was performed, and the skin graft grew after the negative pressure was removed. Good, the patient recovered and was discharged from the hospital after 6 times of dressing change. The wound was treated conservatively with dressing change and wound debridement. The wound gradually healed. During this period, the patient's condition was regularly and regularly assessed by MDT. Blood pressure, blood lipid, hemodialysis, nutritional support and other systemic conditions were adjusted, and the wound was healed. Discharged, hospitalized for 51 days.

Diabetes is rapidly becoming the main cause of global disease burden [15], and it is a group of endocrine and metabolic diseases mainly characterized by disorders of glucose and lipid metabolism. Long-term persistent high blood sugar in diabetic patients will lead to chronic damage and dysfunction and failure of various tissues in the body, especially the eyes, kidneys, heart, blood vessels, nerves and other important organs. (Diabetic Foot, DF) is a complex target organ among many diseases caused by diabetes. Vascular disease, peripheral neuropathy (DPN), and infection are important factors for the occurrence and development of DF, and are one of the main health problems in today's society. Vascular lesions and DPN are the basis of DF pathogenesis, while infection is an independent risk factor that induces or promotes the development of DF. The literature indicates that about 2/3 of DF patients are complicated with neuropathy, about 1/2 suffer from hypertension, retinopathy, and kidney disease, and about 1/4-1/3 have cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, lower extremity vascular disease or dyslipidemia [16]. Traditional single-disciplinary treatment cannot effectively reduce the amputation (limb) rate and mortality of patients, and it is necessary to establish a multidisciplinary collaborative diagnosis and treatment model [17]. DF is associated with multi-system diseases. If these related factors are not corrected in time, the level of amputation (limb) may continue to rise, the wound is difficult to heal, and even life-threatening [18]. With the continuous progress of the social and medical fields, there are more and more effective diagnosis and treatment methods for diabetic foot. The application of MDT in the treatment of diabetic feet is jointly emphasized by the International Diabetic Foot Working Group and many professionals engaged in diabetic feet and related disciplines [19]. MDT is different from the traditional consultation of multiple clinical departments. It refers to the joint participation and discussion of experts from multiple related disciplines in the process of diagnosis and treatment of diseases, and the formulation of individualized treatment plans according to different stages of disease

development, and strict implementation of the treatment plan. disease diagnosis and treatment model [20]. In the traditional multi-department consultation, although different departments diagnose the same patient, there is a lack of communication with each other, and the final treatment plan is still formulated by the attending physician based on his own subject background. On the contrary, MDT includes experts from multiple related departments. The composition of personnel is relatively fixed. Experts from each department communicate in a timely and face-to-face manner. The final plan formulated is comprehensive and efficient. Focusing on MDT can reduce the pressure on each department and avoid waste of medical resources. . The results of this study show that the majority of DF patients are male patients (115, 68.2%), and the ratio of male to female is 2.1:1, which may be due to the lack of estrogen in males to protect blood vessels and poor compliance, smoking and other factors are also factors. Risk factors for inducing DF [21]. Most of the patients were 50-79 years old (78%), the average duration of diabetes was about 8 years, the average duration of diabetic foot disease was 3 months, and the longest duration was 3 years. Studies have pointed out that the duration of diabetes is positively correlated with the incidence of diabetic foot, and age and disease duration are related risk factors for DF [22]. MDT mode and proper blood sugar control are considered essential for the treatment of DF. At the same time, high blood sugar can increase the incidence of wound infection and delay healing [23]. From the perspective of the pathogenesis of DF, it mainly includes diabetic peripheral neuropathy and vascular disease.

Diabetic peripheral neuropathy involves the entire peripheral nervous system, including limbs and visceral nerves, often leading to abnormal sensation, movement, and glandular secretion of the feet, making the feet insensitive to the outside world, uneven force, and insensitive to pain. However, due to the normal motor function of the limbs, the skin of the foot will be repeatedly damaged, resulting in the more common clinical manifestations of DF such as foot infection, gangrene, and osteomyelitis. Charcot joint (Charcot joint) is a relatively serious complication, which is a joint deformity syndrome formed due to peripheral neuropathy, loss of pain sensation, and weight-bearing compression, which leads to joint ligament damage, bone and joint capsule destruction[24]. Changes in the weight-bearing point of the foot often lead to repeated attacks of foot disease. Another important factor is the low perfusion of peripheral nerve blood flow. Nerve ischemia, reduce Na⁺-K⁺-ATPase activity, reduce nerve conduction and regeneration. Long-term high blood sugar stimulation increases intracellular osmotic pressure, leading to swelling, degeneration and even necrosis of nerve cells, resulting in a slowdown of nerve conduction velocity. In this study, diabetic peripheral neuropathy patients accounted for 46.15% (78/169), clinical symptoms of peripheral nerve damage such as symmetrical numbness and coldness of hands, feet and fingers (toes), and disappearance of knee tendon reflex or Achilles tendon reflex, 10 g nylon Monofilament examination, there are symptoms, signs and (or) at least one objective examination abnormality and no obvious other causes of neuropathy; many patients have further occurrence and development of DF due to insufficient understanding of neuropathy and untimely treatment , eventually leading to infection, amputation, etc. The current diagnosis and treatment of DPN include: the use of methylcobalamin, B vitamins (such as VitB12) to nourish the nerves and promote the synthesis of nerve cell proteins, which helps to repair damaged nerves and protect neurons to a certain extent. A large number of studies have shown [25] that the oxidative stress response in DF patients is enhanced, and the oxidation of tissue proteins affects the nerve microcirculation. α -lipoic acid is a powerful antioxidant with relatively reliable curative effect at present[26]. It can increase the levels of CoQ10 and glutathione, reduce endothelial cell damage, thereby protecting the function of endothelial cells in blood vessels and increasing nerve conduction velocity. Diabetic peripheral arterial disease (PAD) usually involves bilateral lower extremities, including macrovascular disease and microvascular disease, and the lesion site is mainly blood vessels below the knee. Diabetic macroangiopathy is mainly due to the long-term high glucose state of blood vessels, forming a large number of glycated end products (AGEs) and low-density lipoprotein apolipoprotein B[27], forming glycosylated low-density apolipoprotein (LDL -ApoB) is deposited in the arterial intima and taken up by endothelial cells. This is the earliest manifestation of arteriosclerosis. When blood sugar is higher than normal, AGEs are produced to accelerate arteriosclerosis and cause blood vessel disease to occur earlier, and the lumen is more likely to become thicker and narrower. Increased intima and media

thickness, plaque formation, and calcification of vessel walls, resulting in narrowing or occlusion of the lumen, as occurs in coronary, cerebral, and peripheral arterial disease [28]. Since most microvessels do not have smooth muscle cells, there is no smooth muscle proliferation and atherosclerotic plaque formation in most diabetic microvascular wall lesions. The main features are endothelial cell damage on the microvascular wall and thickening of the basement membrane, resulting in narrowing of the microvascular lumen Or occlusion; affecting microcirculation, tissue ischemia and hypoxia, nutrients are not easily absorbed, and metabolites cannot be removed [29].

The results of this retrospective analysis showed that arteriosclerosis accounted for 36 cases (36/169) of the 169 cases of DF patients, of which 23 cases (14.4%) had arterial occlusion of the lower extremities. Patients earlier presented with extremity coolness, muscle atrophy, ischemic pain, numbness, weakened or disappeared dorsalis pedis artery pulse, and severe intermittent claudication. Routine use of anticoagulant drugs improves blood coagulation function, and the treatment of beraprost sodium can improve the subjective symptoms of lower limbs in patients with diabetic peripheral vascular disease, such as burning sensation, edema, needle-like pain and paresthesia. Non-invasive blood vessel test (ABI) is used clinically to simply evaluate the vascular condition [30]. When $ABI < 0.9$ indicates ischemia, further examination can be performed to discover vascular lesions and evaluate the vascular condition more accurately. For patients with $ABI > 0.7$, medical treatment should be considered first, such as using sildenafil and other drugs to improve microcirculation, regulate vascular tone, and increase nerve blood flow and oxygen supply to protect nerves. The blood of DF patients has been in a hypercoagulable state for a long time, and the viscosity is higher than that of ordinary people. Therefore, it is particularly important to monitor blood flow, reduce blood viscosity and inhibit platelet aggregation in patients with DM. Patients with severe vascular disease $ABI < 0.7$ (low skin temperature, untouched dorsalis pedis artery) should solve the blood supply problem of the lower extremities as soon as possible [31]. With the development of vascular surgery technology, the amputation rate of DF has decreased significantly. Treatment mainly includes autologous stem cell transplantation, interventional surgery (percutaneous angioplasty, endovascular stent formation, etc.) And stent technology, intracavitary Rutherford grade 3 or above, Fontaine grade IIb or above. Percutaneous balloon dilatation angioplasty (PTA) is recommended as the preferred treatment method, and strives to maximize the opening of occluded vessels and improve blood supply, but the patient's economy is also an important reason hindering the implementation of vascular interventional techniques. Diabetes combined with hyperlipidemia and hypertension are more likely to aggravate arteriosclerosis. Blood sugar, blood pressure, liver and kidney function, and malnutrition are another key factor for the healing of DF patients [32]. Endocrinologists play a leading role in controlling blood sugar, while cardiologists adjust blood pressure and blood lipids in DF patients to keep blood pressure and blood lipids at ideal levels to reduce the incidence of vascular events. For example, statin drugs should be used to control LDL-C below 80mg/dl (2.07mmol/L), and for patients over 40 years old without lower extremity vascular disease, LDL-C should be controlled below 96mg/dl (2.5mmol/L). In this study, the blood lipid level of patients admitted to the hospital was about 3.3 mmol/L before blood lipid treatment, suggesting that most patients had poor blood lipid control. According to the different treatment modes of the MDT group and the non-MDT group, the analysis found that the total cholesterol (TC) of the two groups after the second operation was 3.21 ± 1.05 , 3.52 ± 1.75 mmol/L, and the low-density lipoprotein (LDL-C) were respectively 2.02 ± 0.89 and 2.28 ± 0.75 mmol/L are both statistically significant. Large clinical studies have shown that in diabetic patients without obvious vascular complications, the strategy of using statins to reduce low-density lipoprotein (LDL-C) It can reduce the risk of cardiovascular events [33]. Nutritionists are responsible for providing patients with a balanced nutritional program to meet their needs for micronutrients. The primary goals are to maintain a healthy body weight, achieve and maintain ideal blood glucose levels, reduce HbA1c levels, and reduce cardiovascular disease risk factors (including control of dyslipidemia and hypertension) [34]. Typical microvascular lesions also include retinopathy, nephropathy, and multi-organ lesions of the brain, myocardium, skin, and other tissues [35].

Infection is an important predisposing factor for the occurrence of DF. Since there are many bone and fascia gaps in the foot, once DF is infected, it is easy to develop rapidly along these gaps. Therefore, the importance of opening and draining the infection focus is particularly emphasized [35]. Left untreated may result in fatal sepsis. It is very important to grasp the timing of debridement. Incorrect debridement may lead to aggravation and spread of infection. The area of debridement should not be too large. The necrotic tissue should be removed in stages and in stages. The necrotic tendon should be preserved to the maximum extent during the operation to preserve the patient's health. limb function. Many foreign data show that the gradual removal of necrotic tissue in stages is extremely beneficial to early wound healing [37]. In some patients, the increase of inflammatory indicators such as white blood cells is often not obvious when they are admitted to the hospital, but this cannot be used as a basis for excluding infection. For patients with infection, X-rays are given to confirm whether there is bone abnormality. MRI is recommended when osteomyelitis is suspected. MRI has high sensitivity for the diagnosis of osteomyelitis and is considered to be the most effective imaging technique for evaluating soft tissue infection and osteomyelitis, but its cost is high, and it cannot be used as a first-line clinical examination [38]. Broad-spectrum antibiotics were used in the early stage, and narrow-spectrum and sensitive antibiotics were adjusted in the later stage according to wound culture and drug sensitivity results. Bacterial drug resistance is increasing year by year, which poses a huge challenge for clinicians to use appropriate and effective antibiotics [39]. The presence of microorganisms on the skin surface cannot be used as evidence of DF infection, and bacteria >10⁵CFU is generally used as the basis for diagnosis of infection. In the results of this study, the positive rate of wound culture results was 55.6% upon admission, mainly Gram-negative bacteria accounted for 63.8% (60/94), and Gram-positive bacteria accounted for 31.9% (30/94), of which MRSA In 2 cases, fungi accounted for 4.3% (4/94). After targeted use of antibiotics and effective debridement, the positive rate of bacteria in the two groups decreased by about 20% compared with admission, which was statistically significant. The principle of wound treatment is to remove necrotic tissue, promote the growth of fresh and healthy granulation tissue, and accelerate wound healing. In diabetic patients, some proteases and cytokines that delay wound healing have been considered to be related. For the related factors of delayed wound healing, some new treatment methods are also being explored, such as mechanical debridement, low-frequency Ultrasonic debridement, chemical (enzyme) debridement, biological (maggot) debridement, autolytic debridement, combined debridement, etc. At the same time, a variety of healing-promoting biological means can be applied, such as stem cell therapy, autologous platelet-rich plasma, various growth factors, alginate dressings, antibacterial dressings such as silver ions, etc. Some physical therapy such as hyperbaric oxygen, infrared light and other artificial light source radiation can help wound healing [40]. Negative Pressure Wound Therapy (NPWT) is an effective way to treat acute and chronic wounds in recent years. It is a technology that promotes wound healing by applying negative pressure to the wound (wound).

In 1993, German scholar Fleischmann [41] first proposed that continuous negative pressure suction, flushing, etc., can strongly stimulate granulation growth, improve capillary circulation, stimulate capillary proliferation, significantly increase wound blood flow, reduce infection, and effectively reduce death. The area and volume of the cavity can be eliminated to eliminate dead space and provide favorable conditions for later wound repair (debridement and suture, skin grafting, skin flap, etc.) [42]. However, in the course of clinical use, we found that after using NPWT, some of the normal wounds around the wound gradually became red and ulcerated, which may be the progressive development of DF, and there is also negative pressure suction that affects the blood supply of the affected limb, so the clinical evaluation of the wound should be cautious. Considering the use of NPWT comprehensively, the author uses the intermittent negative pressure suction mode, and the pressure value -50-100mmHg can best play the advantages of NPWT [43]. If the ward conditions only allow the use of uncontrollable central negative pressure, it is recommended to maintain the pressure above 150mmHg. If the pressure is too small, the wound will only form a closed environment instead of a good negative pressure environment, which will easily lead to progressive necrosis of the wound. illness. It has been pointed out in the literature that due to poor vascular conditions in the lower extremities of DF, skin flap

surgery is generally not recommended for wound closure, but some scholars have suggested that skin or skin flap transplantation can be used even in ischemic sites[44]. DF wounds, in this study, there were 35 cases of skin grafting in the MDT group, no flap transplantation cases, 37 cases of skin grafting in the non-MDT group, 2 cases of skin flaps, and 17 cases of direct suture. %, the recurrence rate of the control group was 12.53%, and the data of the two groups were statistically significant. Usually, we decide the amputation plane according to the patient's general condition, local blood supply, injury and examination results, and strive to preserve the function of the affected limb while achieving primary healing of the stump. At present, the most widely used clinically is the measurement of transcutaneous oxygen partial pressure (which can also be combined with vascular imaging examination). >40 mmHg, which indicates that the amputation stump can heal; in between, there is a possibility of healing, and methods of increasing blood flow may be needed [45]. The main advantages of higher amputation planes are lower re-amputation rates and shorter recovery times, with lower amputation planes being associated with higher amputation rates and longer healing times. The toe (limb) amputation rates of the two groups in our department were 17.28% and 37.50%, respectively, which were higher than other reports [46]. The analysis may be due to the lack of awareness of the disease by patients and their families, the toes were black and festered, and the affected limbs could not move. Only go to the hospital for treatment when walking, wound exudate, stench, etc. seriously affect life. The rate of toe (limb) amputation has been significantly improved under MDT treatment. Some scholars [47] found that the use of MDT to treat diabetic feet can reduce the rate of DF amputation (limb) from 23.6% to 9.7%. Nutritional indicators are important indicators for judging the therapeutic effect and prognosis of diabetic foot ulcers. But in actual work, nutritional therapy for diabetes often focuses on how to control diet. There is a lack of domestic research on the role of nutritional support in the healing of diabetic foot ulcers [48]. Much diabetic foot disease is avoidable, good glycemic control and patient education are essential [49]. Clinicians should not only carry out good metabolic control for diabetic patients, but also detect the risk factors of diabetic lower extremity vascular disease and foot disease early. It is very important to strengthen the standardized diagnosis and treatment of diabetic lower extremity vascular disease and foot disease. Strengthen diabetes education and see a doctor in time if necessary. The affected limbs diagnosed with DF should be checked regularly. The low-risk limbs should be inspected once a year, the moderate-risk limbs should be checked every 3-6 months, and the high-risk limbs should be reexamined every 1-2 months[50]. Relieve foot pressure by wearing special diabetic foot shoes, while instructing patients to limit activities (standing, walking), and use crutches when necessary to reduce the risk of skin damage. Pay attention to admission education and provide education for patients and relatives: instruct patients (and relatives or nursing staff) on appropriate self-care and how to recognize and describe related signs, symptoms of infection or worsening (such as fever, changes in local wound status, etc.). Regular follow-up after wound healing and discharge, formulating a comprehensive foot care plan for patients to prevent recurrence. Research shows that the rate of new ulcers after DF is cured (31.6%)[51], while the recurrence rates of the two groups in the three-month follow-up in this study were 4.63% and 12.53%, respectively. intensity and long-term follow-up. Of the 169 DF patients in this group, 75 were cured, 73 were improved, 18 were not cured, and 3 died. The rate of toe (limb) amputation in the MDT group was 17.28% (14/81), the average length of hospitalization was 34.23 days, and the average hospitalization cost was 42,800 yuan, the rate of toe (limb) amputation in the non-MDT group was 37.50% (33/88), the average length of hospital stay was 43.54 days, and the average hospitalization cost was Rs 61,100 per capita. Several aspects, such as MDT, were superior to those of the non-MDT group (the differences were statistically significant, $P<0.05$), which indicated that MDT was used to evaluate and discuss the patient's general condition and condition in the early stage, to clarify the diagnosis and staging, and to formulate corresponding treatment plans. Strict implementation by the corresponding departments is extremely important for the outcome and prognosis of DF patients. At present, many hospitals at home and abroad have applied MDT to the diagnosis and treatment of diabetic foot patients, and achieved certain curative effects [52]. DF is not only a local manifestation of systemic complications of diabetes, but also a very serious and life-threatening acute complication. Clinical treatment should focus on the most prominent problems and deal with them

in stages. Relevant diagnosis and treatment opinions are put forward through regular and regular clinical discussion meetings, and all departments cooperate closely, which is indispensable to exert the maximum effect and improve the treatment effect[53]. To sum up, the MDT treatment of diabetic foot involves a good division of labor among multiple disciplines in clinical practice, in order to minimize the amputation rate and promote wound healing. It is necessary to continue to explore and observe new technologies, new methods, and new models. , Improve the cure rate of diabetic foot patients and the quality of life of patients.

Conclusion

There are more and more diabetic foot patients in diabetes. Because of the high amputation rate and high mortality rate, it harms patients and increases the economic burden of patients, their families and society. Diabetic foot is the outcome of diabetes and a serious complication of diabetes. The condition is complicated and the course of the disease is protracted. Injury, dressing, surgery, vascular reconstruction and other multidisciplinary collaborative diagnosis and treatment models (MDT), so that patients can be treated in a timely manner, can reduce and delay the occurrence of complications, reduce the amputation rate and amputation plane of patients, reduce mortality, and alleviate the pain of patients. mental and economic burden. MDT can effectively shorten the length of hospitalization, reduce hospitalization costs, reduce the rate of toe (limb) amputation, and improve prognosis. It is a treatment model worthy of clinical promotion.

This paper is a retrospective study of clinical data, and there are deficiencies such as small sample size, heterogeneity among patients, and other interfering factors in the wound healing process. We also need to further combine multi-center and big data support, further explore and improve the existing model, so that the obtained data can be better used in clinical practice. There are not many hospitals in Nepal that can implement MDT to treat DF, and it is still a big challenge to popularize it in major hospitals. How to better improve the cure rate of DF, reduce the amputation rate and amputation plane, reduce the mortality rate, and improve the prognosis through MDT is currently a major difficulty, and further exploration and improvement are needed.

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References

- [1] Parker C N, Van Netten J J, Parker T J, et al. Differences between national and international guidelines for the management of diabetic foot disease[J]. *Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews*,2018:e3101.
- [2] J A, K B, van Houtum WH, et al. International consensus and practical guidelines on the management and the prevention of the diabetic foot. International Working Group on the Diabetic Foot[J]. *Current Diabetes Reports*,2003,28(6):225-231.
- [3] Chinese Medical Association Diabetes Branch. Guidelines for Prevention and Treatment of Type 2 Diabetes in China (2017 Edition) [J]. *Chinese Journal of Practical Internal Medicine*, 2018(04):292-344.
- [4] Chiraniya S, Shejol D, Bhagat V, et al. Study of risk factors and outcome of patients with diabetic foot ulcers[J]. *Journal of the Association of Physicians of India*, 2016,64(1):92.
- [5] Lavery L A, Davis K E, Berriman S J, et al. WHS guidelines update: Diabetic foot ulcer treatment guidelines[J]. *Wound repair and regeneration : official publication of the Wound Healing Society [and] the European Tissue Repair Society*, 2016 ,24(1):112.

- [6] Lipsky B A, Aragón-Sánchez J, Diggie M, et al. IWGDF guidance on the diagnosis and management of foot infections in persons with diabetes[J]. *Diabetes/metabolism Research & Reviews*,2016,32(S1):45-74.
- [7] Li Dayong. Multidisciplinary treatment of diabetic foot [Z]. Dandong, Liaoning, China: 20164.
- [8] Bakker K, Apelqvist J, Lipsky B A, et al. The 2015 IWGDF guidance documents on prevention and management of foot problems in diabetes: development of an evidence-based global consensus[J]. *Diabetes/metabolism Research & Reviews*, 2016 ,32 Suppl 1(S1):2.
- [9] Liu Jin, Yuan Xiaoyong, Yuan Geheng, et al. Construction of standard indicators and process for multidisciplinary diagnosis and treatment of diabetic foot disease [J]. *Chinese Journal of Diabetes*, 2018(04):270-279.
- [10] Peng Min, Zhou Qiuhong, Xu Jingcan, et al. Progress in the application of multidisciplinary team diagnosis and treatment model in the diagnosis and treatment of diabetic foot [J]. *Chinese Journal of General Surgery*, 2017(12):1609-1617.
- [11] Diabetes Branch of Chinese Medical Association. Guidelines for Prevention and Treatment of Type 2 Diabetes in China 2013 Edition [J]. *Chinese Journal of Diabetes*, 2014,22(8):2-42.
- [12] Chen Yuxi, Liu Caojie, Zhang Yuwei. Review of important clinical progress in diabetes in 2016 [J]. *Chinese Journal of Practical Internal Medicine*, 2017,37(04):322-325.
- [13] Matiasek J, Domig K J, Djedovic G, et al. The effect of negative pressure wound therapy with antibacterial dressings or antiseptics on an in vitro wound model[J]. *Journal of wound care*,2017,26(5):236 .
- [14] Omar M, Gathen M, Liodakis E, et al. A comparative study of negative pressure wound therapy with and without instillation of saline on wound healing[J]. *J Wound Care*, 2016.
- [15] Vos T, Allen C, Arora M, et al. Global, regional, and national incidence, prevalence, and years lived with disability for 310 diseases and injuries, 1990–2015: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2015[J]. *The Lancet*, 2016, 388(10053):1545-1602.
- [16] Jiang Yufeng, Xu Zhangrong, Fu Xiaobing. The importance of holistic view, system view and multidisciplinary cooperation in the diagnosis and treatment of diabetic foot [J]. *Infection, Inflammation, Repair*, 2012,13(2):67-79.
- [17] Jeong H S, Dominguez A R. Calcipylaxis: Controversies in Pathogenesis, Diagnosis and Treatment [J]. *The American Journal of the Medical Sciences*, 2016, 351(2): 217-227.
- [18] Zhang Yang, Cai Nian, Li Hui, et al. Current status of diagnosis and treatment of lower extremity vascular disease in patients with diabetic foot [J]. *Chinese Journal of Vascular Surgery (Electronic Edition)*, 2018,10(01):61-64.
- [19] Armstrong D G, Boulton A, Bus S A. Diabetic Foot Ulcers and Their Recurrence[J]. *N Engl J Med*,2017,376(24):2367-2375.
- [20] Song P, Wu Q, Huang Y. Multidisciplinary team and team oncology medicine research and development in China[J]. *Bioscience Trends*,2010,4(4):151-160.
- [21] Lin Xiaowen, Li Ling, Xia Yin. Comparison of clinical differences in diabetic foot of different genders [J]. *Journal of Practical Diabetes*, 2017,13(6):59.
- [22] Chinese Medical Association. Diabetes Branch Diabetes Chronic Complications Investigation Group. A 10-year retrospective analysis of chronic complications and related risk factors among inpatients with diabetes mellitus nationwide. *Chinese Journal of Diabetes*, 2003, 11(4): 232-237.
- [23] Buggy A, Moore Z. The impact of the multidisciplinary team in the management of individuals with diabetic foot ulcers: a systematic review. *J Wound Care*. 2017;26:324–339.
- [24] Kaynak G, Birsal O, Gã Ven M F, et al. An overview of the Charcot foot pathophysiology[J]. *Diabetic Foot & Ankle*, 2013, 4(4).
- [25] E B, M L, M K M, et al. Lipoic acid, but not tempol, preserves vascular compliance and decreases medial calcification in a model of elastocalcinosis[J]. "Brazilian journal of medical and biological research", 2014,47(2):119-127.
- [26] Packer L, Witt E H, Tritschler H J. Alpha-lipoic acid as a biological antioxidant[J]. *Free Radic Biol Med*,1995,19(2):227-250.
- [27] Liu Chang, He Yongming, Du Xiaojiao, et al. Correlation between apolipoprotein B/A-1 ratio and type 2 diabetes in Chinese Han population: a cross-sectional study [J]. *Chinese Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 2017, 33(4): 321-325.
- [28] Schaper N C, Van Netten J J, Apelqvist J, et al. Prevention and management of foot problems in diabetes: A Summary Guidance for Daily Practice 2015, based on the IWGDF guidance documents[J]. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract*, 2017, 124:84-92.
- [29] Yazdanpanah L, Shahbazian H, Nazari I, et al. Risk factors associated with diabetic foot ulcer-free survival in patients with diabetes[J]. *Diabetes Metab Syndr*,2018,12(6):1039-1043.

- [30] Zeng Qing, Zeng Xianqiang, Zhai Tao, et al. The significance of comparing ankle-brachial index and toe-brachial index in evaluating the effect of diabetic foot vascular interventional therapy [J]. *Chinese Journal of Diabetes*, 2018, 26(11): 895-899 .
- [31] Zheng Yuehong, Liu Duan. Surgical treatment of diabetic foot vascular disease [J]. *Chinese Journal of Diabetes*, 2016, 8(7):388-391.
- [32] Hingorani A, Lamuraglia G M, Henke P, et al. The management of diabetic foot: A clinical practice guideline by the Society for Vascular Surgery in collaboration with the American Podiatric Medical Association and the Society for Vascular Medicine[J]. *Journal of Vascular Surgery*, 2016, 63(2): 3S-21S.
- [33] Microvascular Complications and Foot Care: Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes-2018[J]. *Diabetes Care*, 2018, 41(Suppl 1): S105-S118.
- [34] Diabetes Branch of Chinese Medical Association, Nutritional Physician Professional Committee of Chinese Medical Doctor Association, Update and Development of Medical Nutrition Therapy for Diabetes in China [J]. *Chinese Journal of Diabetes*, 2015, 7(2):65-67.
- [35] Inzucchi S E, Bergenstal R M, Buse J B, et al. Management of hyperglycemia in type 2 diabetes, 2015: a patient-centered approach: update to a position statement of the American Diabetes Association and the European Association for the Study of Diabetes [J]. *Diabetes Care*, 2015, 38(1):140-149.
- [36] Team I C G. *Diabetic Foot Problems: Prevention and Management*[M]. London: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (UK), 2015.
- [37] Fu Jinfeng, Zhang Mengsi. Prevention and Nursing of Wound Infection[J]. *Chinese Journal of Injury and Repair (Electronic Edition)*, 2015, 10(5).
- [38] IDF Clinical Practice Recommendations on the Diabetic Foot-2017: a guide for healthcare professionals[EB/OL].(2017-05-10)[2017-06-18].
- [39] Pathogen distribution and drug susceptibility analysis of wound infection in patients with diabetic foot [J]. *Chinese Journal of Hospital Infection*, 2017(17).
- [40] Wang Lihua, Li Yan, Luo Yong. Research progress on hyperbaric oxygen therapy for diabetic foot [J]. *Chinese Journal of Diabetes*, 2018, 26(09): 790-792.
- [41] Fleischmann W, Strecker W, Bombelli M, et al. [Vacuum sealing as treatment of soft tissue damage in open fractures][J]. *Unfallchirurg*, 1993, 96(9):488-492.
- [42] Yusuf E, Jordan X, Clauss M, et al. High bacterial load in negative pressure wound therapy (NPWT) foams used in the treatment of chronic wounds[J]. *Wound Repair Regen*, 2013, 21(5):677 -681.
- [43] Borys S, Ludwig-Slomczynska A H, Seweryn M, et al. Negative pressure wound therapy in the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers may be mediated through differential gene expression[J]. *Acta diabetologica*, 2018.
- [44] Md Sohaib A, Arshad Hafeez K, Mohammed Fahud K, et al. Inferiorly based thigh flap for reconstruction of defects around the knee joint.[J]. *Indian journal of plastic surgery : official publication of the Association of Plastic Surgeons of India*, 2014, 47(2).
- [45] Pan Binbin, Ma Jianhua. The application of transcutaneous oxygen partial pressure measurement in the diagnosis and treatment of diabetic foot and peripheral arterial disease[J]. *Chinese Journal of Diabetes*, 2013, 21(12):1142-1143.
- [46] Fu Shimin, Cheng Qingfeng, Deng Shuhua, et al. Analysis of factors related to amputation in patients with diabetic foot ulcers [J]. *Chongqing Medicine*, 2017(23):36-38.
- [47] Shogalefard A, Khorgami Z, Mologen-Tehrain MR, Langam B: Large and deep diabetic heel ulcers need not lead to amputation. *Foot Ankle Int* 2013, 34:215–21.
- [48] Lv Lixue, Huang Lirong, Lao Meiling, et al. Investigation of nutritional status and analysis of influencing factors in elderly patients with diabetic foot ulcers [J]. *Chinese Journal of Nursing*, 2017, 52(3):332-335.
- [49] Weledji E P , Fokam P . Treatment of the diabetic foot – to amputate or not?[J]. *BMC.Surgery*, 2014, 14(1):83.
- [50] Barrett E J, Liu Z, Khamaisi M, et al al. Diabetic Microvascular Disease: An Endocrine Society Scientific Statement [J]. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 2017, 102(12): 4343-4410.
- [51] JiangY, WangX, XiaL, et al. A cohort study of diabetic patients and diabetic foot ulceration patients in China[J]. *Wound Repair Regen*, 2015, 23(2):222-230.
- [52] Buggy A , Moore Z . The impact of the multidisciplinary team in the management of individuals with diabetic foot ulcers: a systematic review[J]. *Journal of Wound Care*, 2017, 26(6):324-339.
- [53] Collins J, Skilton K. Low vision services in South Devon: a multi-agency, multi-disciplinary approach[J]. *Ophthalmic Physiol Opt*, 2004, 24(4):355-359.

